

THE MOST COMMON LANGUAGE LEARNING BARRIERS MANY STUDENTS FACE DUE TO INSUFFICIENT AMOUNT OF VOCABULARY AND SUGGESTED WAYS AND TIPS ON SOLVING THE VOCABULARY PROBLEMS BASED ON CONDUCTED SURVEYS AMONG THE LEARNERS

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Abstract. *The given article describes common problems connected with vocabulary enrichment and acquisition among language learners and puts forward a few ways and methods of effective learning.*

Keywords: *common knowledge, mastering a foreign language, acquiring the knowledge, non-native and unfamiliar language, proficiency in English language, vocabulary development, variety of dilemmas, core component of language proficiency, gaining new lexicon, expressive means of a language, phonetic means, morphological forms, word-building, lexical, phraseological and syntactical forms.*

It is well known that much attention is paid to the development of foreign language skills in students. It is worth noting the fact that the Ministry of Education deals not only with language subjects, but also such subjects as mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology and many others. It should be recognized that not all students succeed in mastering a non-native and unfamiliar language.

In addition to grammar, many learners struggle with mastering the vocabulary of the language they are learning. Mastery of English depends on the knowledge of the vocabulary that learners possess. Although vocabulary development is crucial, it causes many dilemmas, especially for non-native English speakers. Vocabulary is a major component of language proficiency and provides much of the foundation of how learners speak, listen, read, and write. With limited vocabulary and strategies for acquiring new vocabulary, learners can often be denied the most common language learning opportunities around them, such as listening to native speakers or radio, using language in another context, reading, or watching television. In order to realize their language learning potential. The expressive means of language, such as phonetic means, morphological forms, word-formation means, and lexical, phraseological, and syntactic forms, should be considered and given fairly close attention when enriching vocabulary.

Before suggesting ways to solve language-learning tips, one should consider the root of these problems with language learning, so these are the main problems:

- Stuttering
- Hearing loss
- Dysphonia
- Articulation disorders
- Expressive language disorder

- Receptive language disorder
- Doubt about your abilities
- Lack of practice opportunities
- Fear of speaking with strangers
- Loss of Motivation
- Expecting it to be easy
- Peer pressure
- Experience
- Fear of failure
- Lack of self-esteem
- Lack of goals
- Course format
- Poor learner experience

Moreover, it is poor vocabulary. The richer your vocabulary, the easier it is to express your thoughts to the interlocutor, all other things being equal. With a narrow vocabulary, it will be more difficult for you to express yourself, as well as understand the words of an English-speaking friend.

Poor knowledge of grammar. Of course, even knowing the times of the Simple group will already allow you to chat on some simple topics. However, if you want to convey your thoughts to the interlocutor more accurately, the study of more complex grammatical structures cannot be avoided. In addition, in order to perceive English speech by ear in full, you need to understand the intricacies of English grammar.

Lack of practice. If you only speak English for a couple of hours a month and listen for half an hour a week, the appearance of a language barrier should not surprise you. For the systematic development of any skill, whether it be speaking or listening to speech, regular English lessons are needed. Based on the experience of our school, we recommend studying with a teacher at least 2-3 times a week for 60-90 minutes and learning English on your own every day for at least 20-30 minutes. Remember how people learn to drive a car: in order to feel confident behind the wheel, you need to constantly practice. One session a week will not bring the desired result.

Students with poor or limited vocabulary are likely to perform poorly in a variety of subjects related to language skills, linguistics, literature, and translation at the university level of education. This case study focuses on examining the problems or challenges that English language learners face in learning vocabulary at various educational institutions throughout Uzbekistan.

As an experienced teacher, I would suggest different ways to remove language barriers and there are some ways to solve them:

- Tips to overcome the language barrier
- Don't worry if the grammar isn't perfect...
- Don't be afraid to take a pause in the dialogue to formulate a sentence to yourself...
- Feel free to accent...
- Immerse yourself in the language through movies and music...
- Don't worry if you don't know enough words...

- Do not panic if you do not understand the interlocutor

In addition, it also suggests some vocabulary learning strategies to minimize potential problems related to vocabulary comprehension. The data collected through a survey of responses from 25 student participants randomly selected from different levels of English, such as elementary, elementary, intermediate, intermediate, and above advanced. This study was based on an online questionnaire.

The results of the survey showed that students face a number of problems in learning vocabulary, such as fully knowing the meanings of new words, pronouncing new words according to the British and American way of pronunciation, using new words naturally and correctly, remembering and writing new vocabulary, different word forms such as noun, adjective, and verb with words such as: (work, employment, worker, employer, employed, unemployed), etc., and another problem that students face Another not insignificant factor is the improper selection of words for rote learning.

Vocabulary research can be completely divided into three topics, such as selection (prioritization), acquisition (learning), and testing (evaluation). Word selection is one of the most important factors leading to success in learning a foreign language.

Before memorizing certain words that students encounter when reading any material, they should first consider three main factors: first, whether the word is appropriate for their level, second, whether the student knows a simpler form or synonym, and finally, how often the word is used. word, regardless of whether the word is on the list of frequently used words, which these days can be represented by an asterisk next to the word in most modern dictionaries, in short, how active or passive the word is to encourage students to teach.

We must remember the fact that languages are productive; they are constantly creating and adding new words to their vocabulary, and that makes it a little more complex. Consequently, any old-fashioned words should be ignored to a certain level. The experience of language learning has taught many of us to find and use a strategy of guessing the meaning of invisible vocabulary based on context. To expand their vocabulary, learners need to be able to see and hear new words repeatedly through various activities they are likely to otherwise forget, and this can be done in many possible ways, such as immersing themselves in an English speaking environment, publishing a hard - memorizing words on the most prominent places such as the refrigerator, computer or laptop, or having daily chats with friends only in the language they are trying to learn. Instructions given by the tutor in their classes can also be applied to this process. Teachers should avoid using the native language as much as possible and help students feel and participate as actively as possible in the process of learning English.

So, in conclusion, we can be more than confident that much depends on the learners themselves, especially when it comes to vocabulary learning, because it definitely has to do with the tactics and strategies that learners employ, and in addition, learners should be constantly reminded that any language learning is a step-by-step process.

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